

Formulation and Evaluation of Floating Bilayer Tablets using Clarithromycin and Omeprazole for management of gastric ulcer

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Abstract:

With multiple properties to offer a means of a successful drug delivery system, the bilayer tablet represents a new era in the successful development of sustained release drug delivery systems. Bi-layer tablets can be used for both two types of release, where the first layer is an immediate release dose and the second layer is a maintenance dose, as well as for the sequential release of two medications in combination. So, in this current research work an attempt has been made to design floating bilayered tablets using Omeprazole in the immediate layer and Clarithromycin in the sustained layer. For the fabrication of IR (Immediate release) layer to achieve rapid disintegration of OMZ (Omeprazole) super disintegrating agents like Sodium Starch glycolate, Crosscarmellose sodium, Cross povidone were used whereas for second layer i.e.SL (Sustained layer) is loaded with CMN (Clarithromycin) using extract obtained from natural polymer *Abelmoschus Esculent's* and synthetic polymer HPMC K4 were used to release CMN with sustained release manner. Nine formulations were fabricated into floating bilayer tablets. Preformulation studies of blends of both layers were conducted and all the results obtained were found to be within standard specified limits of IP. OMZ IR tablets & CMN SR layer were prepared separately by direct compression method and both the tablets were again fabricated into bilayered tablet. Both the tablets before fabrication into bilayers were subjected to evaluation tests and all the results obtained were found to be within limits of IP. All the nine batches of IR tablets were found to be disintegrated within 40 Seconds. All the batches of SL tablets of CMN were found to be floated more than 8 hours. The high amount of drug release i.e., 98.81 % after 12 hours was seen in the F9 may be due to the both natural & synthetic polymers. So, in this current work we had successfully formulated floating bilayer tablet for which can release with immediate & sustained manner.

Keywords:

Bilayer tablets, Floating tablets, Immediate release, Sustained release

Introduction:

Recent days various developed and developing countries move towards a combination therapy for treatment of various diseases and disorders requiring long term therapy such as hypertension, Diabetes and Cardiovascular diseases¹. Over 90% of the formulations manufactured today are ingested orally. It shows that this class of the formulation is the most popular worldwide and the major attention of the researcher is towards this direction. The major aim of controlled drug delivery is to reduce the frequency of dosing².

Bilayer tablet is the newer a for the successful development of controlled release formulation and better than the traditionally used dosage forms. Bilayer tablet is suitable for sequential release of two drugs in combination it is also capable of separating the two types of incompatible substances and also for sustained release tablet in which one layer is immediate release as initial dose and the second layer is maintenance dose. In certain cases, bilayered tablets have 2 sustain release layers of different drugs³

Advantages:^{4,5}

- Separation of incompatible components
- Patient compliance is enhanced leading to improved drug regimen efficacy
- Maintain physical and chemical stability
- They are a unit dosage form and offer the greatest capabilities of all oral dosage forms for the greatest dose precision and the least content variability

Floating drug delivery system:

Floating drug delivery system are low density system and having bulk density less than gastric fluid and remain they have sufficiently buoyancy to float over the gastric contents and remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a longer period of time⁶

The increase in gastric retention time and a better control of the fluctuations in plasma drug concentrations can be seen. While the system is floating on the gastric content the drug is released slowly at the desire rate reliably buoyant on the surface of the meal. Many buoyant systems developed based on the granules, powder, capsules, tablets, laminated films and hollow microsphere⁷⁻¹²

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Omeprazole was procured from Procured from Scitex Pharmaceuticals Private Limited; Hyderabad and Clarithromycin was procured Rhyme Organics and Chemicals Ltd, Hyderabad. All the remaining excipients used of good standards.

Methods

PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES¹³⁻¹⁶

The following Pre formulation studies are carried out.

Identification of Pure Drugs

This study involves the following parameters

Organoleptic constraints

The APIs were observed for Colour odour, and consistency

Melting point

Melting point of Clarithromycin melting point was determined by an open capillary method.

Analysis of APIs¹⁷⁻¹⁸

Calibration curve of OMZ:

Stock solution of omeprazole was prepared by dissolving 20mg (accurately weighed) of standard omeprazole in 10ml of Methanol. This was further diluted to get a working standard stock solution of 200 μ g/ml. Then 5ml, 10ml, 15ml, 20ml & 25ml of working standard solution were transferred into a series of 10ml volumetric flasks. The volume made up with 6.8 phosphate buffer solution. Then the sample was scan in UV range (200-400), Peak maxima were observed at 298.4 nm. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 298.4 nm against blank, and the calibration curve plotted.

Calibration curve of CMN

Stock solution of Clarithromycin was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of accurately weighed amount of Clarithromycin in 10 ml of ethanol and then the volume was adjusted to 100 ml with the same solution to get 1 mg / ml solution. The stock solution of drug was subsequently diluted with dry ethanol to get 2 μ g, 4 μ g, 6 μ g, 8 μ g and 10 μ g, of drug per ml. Then the sample was scan in UV range (200-400), Peak maxima were observed at 210 nm. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 210 nm against blank, and the calibration curve plotted.

Drug- Excipient Compatibility Studies¹⁹

The compatibility of drugs used with the excipients used was tested by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectrophotometric (FTIR) methods.

Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectral analysis

FTIR spectrums of drugs used with excipients used were obtained individually and in combinations on an FTIR spectrophotometer, (Perkin Elmer, spectrum-100, Japan) using the KBr disk method (2 mg sample in 200 mg KBr). The spectra were obtained by scanning at 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . This spectral analysis was used to check the compatibility of drugs with the polymers used.

Evaluation of Precompression Parameter:

To assess physicochemical properties of the granular blend, all formulations are subjected to pre-formulation studies like bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, compressibility index, Hausner's ratio and particle size distribution⁹.

Angle of Repose:

This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of granules and the horizontal plane. $\theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$ Where, θ = angle of repose h = height of the heap r = radius of the heap

Angle of repose (θ) The angle of repose was determined by using fixed funnel method. The physical mixtures of drug with different excipients were prepared and the accurately weighed drug powder or its physical mixture was taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a way that the tip of the funnel just touches the apex of the heap of the drug powder. The powder was allowed to flow through the funnel freely onto surface. The angle of

repose was calculated using the following equation. $\theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$ Where, h and r are the height and radius of the powder cone respectively.

Bulk density/tapped density

Both loose bulk density (LBD) and tapped density (TBD) were determined were calculated using the following formulas.

LBD = Powder weight/volume of the packing

TBD = Powder weight /tapped volume of the packing

Compressibility index:

The compressibility index of the granules was determined by Carr's compressibility index.

Carr's index (%) = $[(TBD - LBD)/TBD] \times 100$.

Hausner's ratio:

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of measuring the powder flow.

It was calculated by the following formula.

Hausner's ratio = Tapped density/Bulk density

Preparation of immediate release layer of Omeprazole:

Omeprazole immediate release layer were prepared by direct compression method variable using super disintegrants such as, croscarmellose sodium (Ac-DiSol), Crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate at three concentrations. Omeprazole was weighed and passed (sieve) through mesh no. 40. croscarmellose sodium (Ac-DiSol), cross povidone, sodium starch glycolate and lactose were passed (sieve) through mesh no. 60. The active ingredient, croscarmellose sodium (Ac-DiSol), cross povidone, sodium starch glycolate and lactose were mixed in a poly bag for 5 minutes. Magnesium stearate previously passed through mesh no. 60 was mixed well in a poly bag for 3 minutes. The blend was directly compressed using single punch tablet compression machine. The composition of Omeprazole tablet layer is shown in Table 1

Table 1: Formulation of Omeprazole IR tablets

Component	Formulation Code								
	IR 1	IR2	IR3	IR4	IR5	IR6	IR7	IR8	IR9
Omeprazole (OMZ)	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Sodium Starch glycolate	5	7.5	10						
Croscarmellose sodium				5	7.5	10			
Crospovidone							5	7.5	10
Lactose	44	41.5	39	44	41.5	39	44	41.5	39
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Magnesium stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Total weight	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Method for preparation of clarithromycin floating tablet:

Sustained release layers of CMN were prepared using varying the concentration of AEFM, HPMCK4M by direct compression method. CMN was weighed and passed (sieve) through mesh no. 40. AEFM, HPMCK4, PVP K34, sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, lactose was weighed and passed (sieve) through mesh no. 60. CMN, AEFM, HPMCK4, sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, lactose was mixed in a poly bag for 5 minutes. Magnesium stearate previously passed through mesh no. 60 was mixed well in a poly bag for 3 minutes. The

blend was directly compressed using single punch tablet compression machine (Cadmach). The composition of CMN tablet layer is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Composition of the Clarithromycin gastro retentive layer

Ingredients	Formulations								
	CSR1	CSR2	CSR3	CSR4	CSR5	CSR6	CSR7	CSR8	CSR9
Clarithromycin (CMN)	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
AEFM (mg)				160	170	180	80	85	90
HPMC K 4	160	170	180				80	85	90
PVP K30	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Citric acid	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
NaHCO ₃	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Lactose	40	30	20	40	30	20	40	30	20
Total weight	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500	500

Evaluation of Post Compression Parameter

Both layered tablets prepared Thickness:

Three tablets were picked from each formulation randomly and thickness was measured individually using Vernier-caliper. It is expressed in mm and standard deviation was also calculated.

Hardness

For each formulation, the hardness of five tablets was determined using the Monsanto hardness tester and measured in terms of kg/cm².

Weight variation

Twenty tablets were selected randomly from each formulation and average weight was determined. The tablets were weighed individually and compared with average weight.

Friability

A sample of twenty randomly selected tablets were accurately weighed and placed in a Roche friabilator. The friabilator was operated for 4 min at a speed of 25 rpm. The tablets were removed from the friabilator, de-dusted and reweighed. The percent loss in weight due to abrasion and impact was calculated as,

$$\% \text{ Friability} = (\text{Loss in weight} / \text{Initial weight}) \times 100$$

Drug content for IR tablet

Ten randomly selected tablets from each formulation (F1 to F9) were finely powdered and Drug equivalent to 10 mg of drug dissolved in 10 ml 0.1 N HCl (simulated gastric fluid of pH 1.2 without enzymes) sonicate it for 20 minutes, till the entire drug leached out from complex, then the solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41. From this Solution take 1 ml and Diluted up to 100 ml with 0.1 N HCl and the drug content was determined spectrophotometrically at 301 nm for Omeprazole.

Drug content for SR tablet

Twenty tablets were taken and amount of drug present in each tablet was determined. The tablets were crushed in a mortar and the powder equivalent to 100mg of drug was transferred to 100ml standard flask. The powder was dissolved in 50 ml of 0.1 N HCL and made up to volume with of 0.1 N HCl. The sample was mixed thoroughly and filtered through a 0.45 μ membrane filter. The filtered solution was diluted suitably and react with dye and analysed for drug content by UV spectrophotometer at a λ max of 210 nm using of 0.1 N HCL as blank.

Fabrication of Gastroprotective Bilayer tablet:

As the upper punch was raised the immediate release layer of OMZ tablet was placed on the above the sustained release layer of CMN; the 2 layers were then compressed into a floating bilayer tablet. Each tablet weighed 600mg containing 40 mg OMZ and 250 mg CMN.

Simultaneous estimation of Omeprazole and Clarithromycin in bilayer tablet

Powder equivalent to 40 mg of Omeprazole and 250 mg of Clarithromycin was weighed accurately and transferred to 1000 ml volumetric flask. Sufficient quantity of distilled water was added to dissolve the drugs completely. Volume was adjusted to 1000 ml with distilled water. 1 ml of this solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. Absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 301 and 210 nm. Concentration was determined by UV-spectrophotometry by simultaneous estimation method. The values of drug content of OMZ tablet layer and CMN tablet layer are shown in Table respectively. The drug content of optimized bilayer tablet is reported in Table

In vitro buoyancy studies:

In vitro buoyancy was determined by floating lag time as per the method described by Rosa et al. The tablets were placed separately in a 100 ml glass beaker containing simulated gastric fluid (SGF), pH 1.2 as per USP. The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating lag time

Dissolution rate studies of SR tab:

In vitro drug release of the sample was carried out using USP- type II dissolution apparatus (Paddle type). The dissolution medium, 900 ml 0.1N HCl was placed into the dissolution flask maintaining the temperature of 37 \pm 0.50c and rpm of 75. One Clarithromycin tablet was placed in each basket of dissolution apparatus. The apparatus was allowed to run for 10 hours. Sample measuring 5 ml were withdrawn after every 1 hour up to 10 hours using 10ml pipette. The fresh dissolution medium (37 \pm 0.50C) was replaced every time with the same quantity of the sample. From this take 0.5 ml and dilute up to 10 ml with 0.1 N HCL, react with dye (methyl orange) and extract with chloroform and take the absorbance at 416.0 nm using spectroscopy

Dissolution rate studies of Bilayer tab:

In vitro drug release was performed according to the USP dissolution apparatus II at 50 rpm and $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ temperature over a 12 hrs periods for clarithromycin SR and 1 hr for Omeprazole IR, using an automated paddle dissolution system (Lab India). A minimum of 6 tablets per batch were tested. The media used was 0.1N HCl at a pH 1.2 and a volume of 900 ml was maintained at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Test sample (1ml) was withdrawn at particular time interval and replaced with fresh dissolution media maintained at the same temperature and the concentration of dissolved drug was determined using U.V. (Ultraviolet Labindia 3000+) spectrophotometer at λ_{max} 301 nm for Omeprazole and 210 nm for clarithromycin respectively

Results and Discussion:**IDENTIFICATION OF PURE DRUGS****Organoleptic properties of Drugs used**

The colour, odour, and consistency of the pure drug procured is the primary confirmation of their purity. The organoleptic properties of pure drug used were shown in table 3.

Table 3: Organoleptic properties

Property	Inference	
	CMN	OMZ
Nature	Powder	Powder
Colour	Yellowish white	White
Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic

The organoleptic properties of the CMN were as per their monographs in Indian Pharmacopoeia.

Results of melting point

One more approach of assessing the purity of the CMN was determination of melting of this drug. The details of drugs depicted in table 4

Table 4: Melting point of API used

Drug	Actual Melting point($^\circ\text{C}$)	Observed melting point ($^\circ\text{C}$)
CMN	222-225	223.8 ± 2.3
OMZ	156-160	157 ± 1.9
Values in mean \pm SD; trials (n)=3		

The melting points of CMN & OMZ were as per the Indian Pharmacopoeia, which confirms that the drug was pure and maintaining standards.

ANALYSIS OF DRUG USED

The calibration curve is the main requirement for finding the concentration of drug in a sample and they were represented in table 5 & fig.3 for CMN

Table 5: Concentration vs. absorbance values for the estimation of OMZ

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.101
20	0.202
40	0.412
80	0.511
100	0.599
120	0.689
140	0.705
160	0.908

Figure 1: Calibration curve of OMZ

The Calibration curve for OMZ represents slope $(y) = 0.0047 + 0.1223$ with regression (R^2) value of 0.9562, indicates the linearity.

Table 6: Concentration vs. absorbance values for the estimation of CMN

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.11
20	0.202
40	0.311

80	0.422
100	0.568
120	0.689
140	0.801
160	0.908

Fig.2: Standard calibration c

urve of CMN

The Calibration curve for CMN represents slope $(y) = 0.0051X + 0.0736$ with regression (R^2) value of 0.9891, indicates the linearity.

DRUG- EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES

Fourier Transform Infra-Red spectral analysis

Figure 3: FTIR Spectrum of OMZ

Figure 4: FTIR Spectrum of OMZ & Excipients

Table 7: The absorption ranges for OMZ alone and its blend with excipients

Bond type	Actual Absorption Range (cm^{-1})	Observed range of pure drug (cm^{-1})	
		OMZ	OMZ+ excipients
O – H	3600-3200	3598.51	3534.14
C – H	3300-2800	3016.01	3112.84
C = O	1800-1630	1768.45	1690.10

The characteristic peaks and stretches in the FTIR spectrum of OMZ with carrier were found undisturbed indicating the compatibility of carriers used with OMZ.

Figure. 5: FTIR spectrum of CMN and CMN + Excipients

Table 8: The absorption ranges for CMN alone and its blend with excipients

Bond type	Actual Absorption Range (cm ⁻¹)	Observed range of pure drug (cm ⁻¹)	
		CMN	CMN+ excipients
O – H	3600-3200	3498.51	3467.16
C – H	3300-2800	3126.03	3124.84
C = O	1800-1630	1768.45	17.84.51

The characteristic peaks and stretches in the FTIR spectrum of CMN with carrier were found undisturbed indicating the compatibility of carriers used with CMN.

Table 9: Results of precompression parameters of OMZ IR tablets

F Code	Bulk density(gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Compressibility index	Hausner's ratio
F1	0.582±0.002	0.732±0.007	27.33±0.73	0.721±0.01
F2	0.581±0.008	0.730±0.006	28.33±0.72	0.723±0.01
F3	0.576±0.002	0.728±0.005	27.30±0.68	0.720±0.01
F4	0.570±0.007	0.729±0.003	29.30±0.65	0.726±0.03
F5	0.580±0.003	0.735±0.004	30.30±0.61	0.730±0.04
F6	0.585±0.003	0.732±0.006	32.80±0.64	0.728±0.06
F7	0.582±0.004	0.742±0.003	36.24±0.70	0.720±0.03
F8	0.579±0.002	0.792±0.005	29.72±0.68	0.720±0.04
F9	0.584±0.004	0.768±0.004	28.52±0.71	0.739±0.03

Table 10: Results of precompression parameters of CMN SR tablets

F Code	Bulk density(gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Compressibility index	Hausner's ratio
F1	0.582±0.002	0.732±0.007	27.33±0.73	0.721±0.01
F2	0.581±0.008	0.730±0.006	28.33±0.72	0.723±0.01
F3	0.576±0.002	0.728±0.005	27.30±0.68	0.720±0.01
F4	0.570±0.007	0.729±0.003	29.30±0.65	0.726±0.03
F5	0.580±0.003	0.735±0.004	30.30±0.61	0.730±0.04
F6	0.585±0.003	0.732±0.006	32.80±0.64	0.728±0.06
F7	0.582±0.004	0.742±0.003	36.24±0.70	0.720±0.03
F8	0.579±0.002	0.792±0.005	29.72±0.68	0.720±0.04
F9	0.584±0.004	0.768±0.004	28.52±0.71	0.739±0.03

Table 11: Results of Post-Compression Parameters of OMZIR Tablets

F Code	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	weight variation (%)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Disintegration (sec)
F1	3.5	0.486	100	2.1	97.51	180±5
F2	3.6	0.851	100	2.3	97.15	120±6
F3	3.4	0.764	100	2.2	98.15	100±7
F4	3.5	0.897	100	2.1	98.25	170±8
F5	3.6	0.744	100	2.4	97.85	90±5
F6	3.4	0.654	100	2.3	98.80	130±6
F7	3.5	0.456	100	2.2	96.45	140±7
F8	3.4	0.651	100	2.1	97.25	150±8
F9	3.4	0.743	100	2.3	96.12	100±4

Table 12: Results of post compression parameters of CMN sustained release tablets

F Code	Thickness	Hardness	Weight variation	Friability	Drug content	Total floating	Floating lag time
F1	3.53±0.05	4.8	500.19±2.94	0.58 ± 0.10	98.33± 0.92	>8	28Sec
F2	3.94± 0.10	4.4	500.17± 3.77	0.52±0.08	96.20±0.33	>8	25Sec
F3	3.96± 0.05	4.5	500.30±3.30	0.39±0.12	99.60±1.41	>8	33 Sec
F4	3.95± 0.05	4.7	500.28±1.50	0.18±0.04	98.14±1.21	>8	35 Sec
F5	3.93± 0.10	5.2	500.18±3.11	0.33±0.07	96.21±1.07	>8	36 Sec
F6	4.03± 0.06	5.3	500.16±2.33	0.28±0.05	95.50±1.79	>8	35 Sec
F7	4.05± 0.05	4.8	500.02±2.11	0.31±0.08	98.21±0.34	>8	31 Sec
F8	3.98± 0.05	4.5	500.12±2.83	0.36±0. 12	98.11±0.90	>8	30 Sec
F9	3.69±0.06	4.9	500.10±2.83	0.32±0.09	97.83±0.56	>8	31 Sec

Table 13: In-vitro Drug Release Study of OMZ IR Tablets

Time(h)	% Cumulative Drug Release								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
5	35.1	33.10	37.1	34.12	36.15	38.12	39.12	40.12	41.12
10	60.2	65.2	67.12	61.12	62.12	65.11	68.16	70.11	71.13
15	90.5	95.8	98.1	96.3	97.1	98.20	96.15	97.15	98.3

Table 14: In-vitro Drug Release Study of CMN GRF Tablets

Time(hr)	% Cumulative Drug Release								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0.5	34.65	32.56	30.45	28.18	27.12	21.19	25.12	26.10	26.12
1	45.74	39.12	37.89	34.62	33.54	30.20	32.54	32.15	31.45
1.5	55.68	48.13	47.98	43.12	43.21	39.11	41.25	45.12	40.12
2	69.97	61.18	51.12	48.13	51.15	47.15	49.32	51.18	48.15
3	98.28	88.61	69.89	62.14	61.13	58.16	59.32	61.11	60.12
4		99.41	89.12	79.85	77.12	69.13	69.54	75.15	76.65
6			98.78	88.12	85.14	77.12	78.12	79.11	84.15
8				98.18	89.12	85.18	89.31	85.10	89.16
12					91.11	92.10	97.10	98.13	98.81

Figure. 5: % Drug Release of CMN GRF Tablets.

Conclusion:

In the present work an attempt had been made to develop bilayered tablets with OMZ for IR and CMN for SR. The research works relates to formulation and development of oral bilayer tablet of esomeprazole and clarithromycin for administration of therapeutically and prophylactically effective amount of drug substance to obtain both a relatively quick onset of therapeutic effect and maintenance of a therapeutically active plasma concentration for relatively long period of time. Research conclude that Bi-layer tablet is suitable for delivering drugs with different release pattern with one layer of drug as immediate release to get quick relief and second drug as sustained release of drug which gives effect of drug for sufficient time and reduce frequency of dose.

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